

Orbital Symmetry Influences on some Cross-bridge Electronic Interactions and Electron Transfer Rates

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Kinetic studies of Ti^{III} reduction of Co^{III} and Ru^{III} oxidants, and electrochemical and spectroscopic studies of diruthenium complexes that are analogs for the transition states of those reactions, lead to the conclusion that dihydroxyquinolate anions provide a moderate degree of cross-bridge coupling between metal t_{2g} orbitals, so that rate constants for electron transfer between such orbitals can be measured on the stopped-flow time scale.

Electron-transfer (ET) reactions involving transition metal complexes¹ may be considered according to the symmetry of electron-donor and electron-acceptor orbitals. Reduction of low-spin d^6 Ru^{III} complexes by d^1 Ti^{III} involves t_{2g} metal orbitals as both electron-donor and electron-acceptor orbitals, while reduction of low-spin d^6 Co^{III} complexes by high spin d^4 Cr^{II} involves e_g metal orbitals as both electron-donor and electron-acceptor orbitals. This difference has considerable influence on kinetics and mechanism.

For instance, in e_g-e_g $Co^{III}L-Cr^{II}$ reactions, when L is Cl^- , an inner-sphere mechanism prevails and the rate constant ($k_{Cl} = 6 \times 10^5 s^{-1} M^{-1}$) is much higher² than that observed when L is CH_3COO^- ($k_{OAc} = 0.97 s^{-1} M^{-1}$), but conversely, in $t_{2g}-t_{2g}$ $Ru^{III}L-Ti^{III}$ reactions, an opposite effect is observed; the rate constant for the acetate-oxidant ($k_{OAc} = 7 \times 10^3 s^{-1} M^{-1}$, substitution-limited inner-sphere mechanism)³ is much larger than that for the chloro-oxidant ($k_{Cl} = 12 s^{-1} M^{-1}$, outer-sphere mechanism)¹. The rate constant for intramolecular $t_{2g}-t_{2g}$ ET within the Creutz-Taube ion ($[A_6Ru(prz)RuA_6]^{5+}$, where $A = NH_3$, $prz = pyrazine$)⁵ is even larger. The estimated⁶ value is $k_e = 10^8 s^{-1}$. Factors other than orbital symmetry are also important, however. For instance, the Ti^{III} reduction of A_6Ruprz^{5+} takes place⁷ through an outer-sphere mechanism with $k = 10^5 s^{-1} M^{-1}$, rather than an inner-sphere mechanism. The reaction has a large driving force (0.5 V) and the rate constant for outer-sphere ET is larger than that of substitution on Ti^{III} ($k_{sub} < 10^3 s^{-1} M^{-1}$), so that inner-sphere ET cannot occur, although one would expect a high rate of inner-sphere ET in this case.

The rate variations indicated above can readily be rationalised. Chloride provides a LUMO with σ symmetry which is expected to overlap effectively with metal e_g orbitals but not with t_{2g} orbitals. On the other hand, acetate and pyrazine provide LUMOs with π symmetry which are expected to overlap effectively with metal t_{2g} orbitals, but not with e_g orbitals. The symmetry fit between bridging ligand LUMO

and metal HOMO and the symmetry of the LUMO of the bridging ligand are both important in determining the rate of ET in inner-sphere reactions. In addition rates of substitution processes play a role in deciding whether inner-sphere or outer-sphere mechanisms prevail.

Chloranillic acid (hereafter H_2CQ) and 2,5-dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone (hereafter H_2BQ) are interesting potential bridging ligands, since they can provide moderate distances between electron-donor and electron-acceptor atoms and also low-energy empty π orbitals, but rotation around the bridging ligand (which complicates interpretations of other reactions⁸) is not possible without breaking chemical bonds. Any barrier to ET in the Ti^{III} reduction of $Ru(\text{trien})CQ^+$ would be expected to result from orbital symmetry and energy effects.

The electronic coupling between two nickel ions (e_g-e_g) through a bridging oxalate⁹ is $J = -16 cm^{-1}$, while the couplings through a bridging CQ and a bridging 1,4-dihydroxynaphthoquinone are only $-1.0 cm^{-1}$ and $-0.1 cm^{-1}$, respectively^{10,11}. The coupling between two titanium ions ($t_{2g}-t_{2g}$) through a bridging oxalate¹² is $-36 cm^{-1}$, only about twice as large as that between two nickel ions (e_g-e_g). This suggests that the change of metal-orbital symmetry will not greatly affect the electronic interaction through a common bridging ligand, while the change of bridging-ligand orbital symmetry and/or energy will have a major effect. As a comparison, the coupling between two ruthenium ions ($t_{2g}-t_{2g}$) through a bridging pyrazine (the Creutz-Taube ion), is calculated¹³ to be $-2 \times 10^3 cm^{-1}$, and the intramolecular ET rate constant is estimated to be $k_{et} \geq 10^8 s^{-1}$. Based on these considerations, the electronic coupling between Ru^{III} and Ti^{III} through bridging CQ would be expected to be rather small and low intramolecular ET rate is a possibility.

Diruthenium complexes with dihydroxybenzoquinolate ligands as bridges are related to the dinuclear complexes formed in the reactions repor-

ted above. Mixed-valence diruthenium complexes of this sort would be closely analogous to the transition states expected for those reactions. Ernst and coworkers¹⁶ prepared a series of tertrabipyridinediruthenium semiquinone complexes, Merrill¹⁷ prepared tertrabipyridinediruthenium complexes with the dianion of 1,4-dihydroxyanthraquinone (quinazarin, a dihydroxyquinone with three aromatic rings) as bridging ligand, and Sadler and Gordon¹⁸ prepared a series of tertrabipyridinediruthenium complexes that included the dianion of 1,5-dihydroxyanthraquinone (anthrarufin, an isomer of quinazarin) as bridging ligand. Dei and coworkers¹⁹ used the dianion of 5,8-dihydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (naphthazarin, hereafter H₂NQ, a dihydroxyquinone with two aromatic rings) as a bridging ligand. In these diruthenium complexes, an absorption band in the near infrared spectrum serves to identify mixed-valence compounds, and to gauge the extent of cross-bridge electronic interaction.

Results and Discussion

Since chloranillic acid (and 2,5-dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone) can be reduced by Ti^{III}, it is possible that the ET reaction between Ru(trien)CQ⁺ and Ti^{III} might involve a 'chemical mechanism' (the Ti^{III} first reduces the bridging ligand CQ, and then the reduced ligand reduces Ru^{III}, rather than a 'resonance mechanism' (the odd electron on Ti^{III} transfers directly from Ti^{III} to Ru^{III} through the bridging ligand). To test this possibility, we studied the kinetics of the redox reactions between Co(en)₂SQ⁺ and Ti^{III} and between Co(trien)BQ⁺ and Ti^{III}. Squaric acid cannot be reduced by Ti^{III} but is similar in geometry to 2,5-dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone. The LUMO energies calculated for SQ²⁻ and BQ²⁻ are the same, while the LUMO energy calculated for SQ²⁻ is about 1.5 eV higher than that for BQ²⁻.

The Ti^{III} reduction of Co(en)₂SQ⁺ follows first order kinetics but rate constants (*k*_{obs}) are not linearly dependent on either [Ti^{III}] or [H⁺]⁻¹. This reaction involves rate-limiting ET from Ti^{III} to Co^{III} through the bridging ligand. Reduction of Co(trien)BQ⁺ by Ti^{III} involves two stages—a faster absorbance-decrease (*k*_t) followed by a slower absorbance-decrease (*k*_a). The values of *k*_t are linearly dependent on [Ti^{III}], but independent of acidity. The values of *k*_a are linearly dependent both on [Ti^{III}], and on [H⁺]⁻¹. The difference in kinetics between the Ti^{III} reduction of Co(en)₂SQ⁺ and that of Co(trien)BQ⁺ can be interpreted as being due to the circumstance that the latter reaction does *not* involve a deprotonation after formation of the intermediate, Co(trien)BQTi⁴⁺. The best explanation for this is that the intermediate contains a reduced form of the bridging ligand (the 'chemical mechanism'). That is, the formation of the intermediate is followed by a fast ET from the Ti^{III} *t*_{2g} orbital to the bridging ligand LUMO. The ET rate is fast enough so that a deprotonation reaction does not occur prior to ET. The intermediate

should then be written as [Co^{III}(trien)BQ-Ti^{IV}]⁴⁺, rather than as [Co^{III}(trien)BQTi^{III}]⁴⁺. The rate-limiting step in this mechanism is ET from the one-electron reduced bridging ligand to the cobalt(III) metal center.

The difference in mechanism between the reductions of the two Co^{III} complexes is ascribed to the difference in the reducibilities of the two bridging ligands. Reduction of Ru(trien)CQ⁺ by Ti^{III} follows first order kinetics. Values of *k*_{obs} are independent of acidity and proportional to [Ti^{III}] at low [Ti^{III}]. As [Ti^{III}] increases, the slope of *k*_{obs}-[Ti^{III}] curve gradually decreases. The mechanism that obtains is

with *K* = 59 M⁻¹ and *k*_{et} = 1.1 × 10² s⁻¹. The activation enthalpy associated with *k*_{et} is about half of that associated with substitution on the first coordination sphere of Ti^{III}, while the activation entropy associated with *k*_{et} is about twice as large as that associated with substitution on Ti^{III}. This indicates that this reaction is *not* substitution-limited. The bridging ligand LUMO has the same symmetry as the Ru^{III} *t*_{2g} orbital, so ET to the ligand is not distinguishable from ET to the metal. The rate-limiting step is ET through the bridging CQ from Ti^{III} to Ru^{III} (the 'resonance mechanism'). Slowness of intramolecular ET in the reduction of Ru(trien)CQ⁺ must be ascribed to a low value of the electronic transmission coefficient.

The intramolecular ET rate constant in the Ti^{III} reduction of Ru(trien)CQ⁺ (*k*_{et} = 10² s⁻¹) is 10² smaller than the lower limit of that in the Ti^{III} reduction of Ru(NH₃)₄C₂O₄⁺ (*k*_{et} > 10⁴ s⁻¹) and 10⁶ smaller than that in the Creutz-Taube ion (*k*_{et} = 10⁸ s⁻¹). Molecular-orbital calculations show that bridging CQ has a LUMO with *b*_{2g} symmetry (in the D_{2h} point group), bridging pyrazine has LUMO with *b*_{1u} symmetry and bridging naphthoquinone has a LUMO with *a*_u symmetry. The (*d*_{zx}, *d*_{yz}) orbitals from each cation can form an in-phase combination with *b*_{1u} symmetry and out-of-phase combinations with *b*_{2g} or *a*_u symmetry. In the pyrazine-bridged species, the *d*_{zx} orbitals from each metal can form an in-phase combination with *b*_{1u} symmetry. No other combinations will yield such symmetries.

Since an in-phase combination has lower energy than an out-of-phase combination, the most effective bridging ligand would be one that has a LUMO that can interact with the in-phase combination of the two metal *t*_{2g} orbitals^{14,15}. The in-phase combinations of metal orbitals can overlap effectively with pyrazine LUMOs, which, in turn, provide pathways for strong electronic interaction between electron-donor and electron-acceptor orbitals. For the quinone bridging-ligands, the electron-donor

and electron-acceptor orbitals must interact through an out-of-phase combination. This would be expected to give somewhat lower electronic interaction. Since calculations show that the bridging CQ and naphthoquinone have the same LUMO energy and require similar out-of-phase combination of metal t_{2g} orbitals, we would expect similar electronic interactions in reactions involving these two ligands.

As in the systems studied by Dei and coworkers, a peak at negative potentials in the cyclical voltammograms of the BQ dimers can be assigned to reduction of the ligand (BQ^{2-}). The more anodic redox processes can be interpreted to yield a comproportionation constant of 4×10^9 for formation of the mixed-valence species. Class II complexes should have values less than 200 for that quantity²⁰, but strongly coupled class III complexes should have values in the range $10^6 - 10^{13}$. This result indicates that the metal atoms in tetrabipyridyl-diruthenium complexes with 2,5-dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone bridging ligands interact significantly.

There is only one band beyond 800 nm in the uv-visible spectra of any of the diruthenium BQ complexes. There is a peak at 990 nm with extinction coefficient of $110 \text{ cm}^{-1} M^{-1}$ for the green tripositive complex that is not present in the spectra of either the dipositive or tetrapositive ions. This is in the region in which metal-quinone charge transfer peaks are found, but this peak has an extinction coefficient that is much lower than such bands generally have. If we tentatively adopt the interpretation that the green compound is a mixed-valence species, this band can be taken as an intervalence charge transfer (IVCT) band. The half-width of this band was estimated as 2500 cm^{-1} , using only the low-energy side of the band (to avoid interference of the intense band at 624 nm). The half-width predicted by the Hush²¹ treatment is 4830 cm^{-1} .

This deviation suggests that there is stronger cross-bridge coupling in the BQ system than in the typical class II compounds for which the Hush formulation is derived. On this basis, the ion of present interest should be assigned to class III. Using 8.0 \AA as the Ru—Ru distance in the tripositive cation and the position and intensity of the IVCT band for that cation, one obtains a value of 0.013 for the mixing coefficient that measures the metal-metal interaction energy. This is also consistent with a class III formulation for this ion.

This result on the mixed-valence diruthenium complex is consistent with the kinetic results on the $Ru^{III}-Ti^{III}$ ET reactions. (The mixed-valence diruthenium complex is a close analog to the transition state of the Ti^{III} reduction of $Ru(\text{trien})CQ^+$). All the data support the conclusion that dihydroxyquinone anions support an *intermediate* degree of cross-bridge electronic coupling between t_{2g} orbitals, so that rates of intramolecular $Ru^{III}-Ti^{III}$ ET are measurable on the stopped-flow time scale.

Experimental

$Ru(\text{trien})CQ^+$, $Co(\text{en})_2SQ^+$ and $Co(\text{trien})Q^+$ were synthesised and characterised by standard techniques. (Trien is triethylenetetramine ($C_6H_{18}N_4$), en is ethylenediamine ($C_2H_8N_2$) and CQ^{2-} , BQ^{2-} , SQ^{2-} are the dianions of chloranillic acid ($C_6H_2O_4Cl_2$), 2,5-dihydroxy-benzoquinone ($C_6H_4O_4$) and squaric acid ($C_4H_2O_4$)). Trien and en were used to prevent polymerisation. Molecular orbital symmetries and energies of $C_2O_4^{2-}$, CQ^{2-} , BQ^{2-} , SQ^{2-} , pyrazine and NQ^{2-} were calculated using the extended Hückel theory. Using methods to be described more fully elsewhere, we prepared several tetrabipyridinediruthenium compounds involving the anion of 2,5-dihydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone (BQ^{2-}) of formulas $[Ru_2(\text{bpy})_4BQ](PF_6)_n$, where n ranges from 2 to 4. Electrochemical and kinetic measurements were carried out as described¹. In deaerated dry acetonitrile at 25° reversible redox couples were observed by cyclical voltammetry using glassy carbon electrodes. All complexes were ESR silent at both 77 and 300 K.

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